

A Comparative Analysis of Spatial Filtering and CEBRA Methodologies for Enhancing BCI Adaptability on ECoG Data

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Abstract

Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) hold great potential to transform lives of those with motor impairments, but their efficacy is constrained by individual neural variability. Neural data is highly complex, so we chose a linear and non-linear filtering method to compare their adaptability. Robust and adaptive decoding methods are crucial for preparing and optimizing neural data, ensuring its interpretability and accessibility for BCIs. This study compares two approaches for electrocorticography (ECoG) data processing: Linear Spatial Filtering and Consistent Embeddings of High-Dimensional Behavioral and Recordings (CEBRA). Spatial Filtering significantly improved the average signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) for one subject from 3.1 dB to 8.3 dB; however, the extracted features exhibited poor class separability, resulting in weak classification performance. On the other hand, CEBRA successfully identified distinct latent patterns and preserved relevant data structures but lacked generalizability needed for reliable stimulus classification on new subjects. These findings suggest that neither method alone is

sufficient, revealing the need for additional processing techniques or hybrid approaches to improve BCI adaptability.

Description

Electrocorticographic (ECoG) signals for motor tasks are rich but highly complex. The broad spatial and spectral features of ECoG recordings mean that different studies often select widely varying signal components and decoding models (Volkova et al., 2019; Saibene et al., 2024; Saeidi et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021). While linear models (Parra et al., 2005; Jas et al., 2018; Hu et al., 2007; Whitmer et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2015) like spatial filtering (Schaworonkow & Voytek, 2021) offer simplicity, they may miss the nonlinear structure of neural data. Nonlinear methods such as CEBRA (Schneider et al., 2023) aim to uncover shared latent spaces without heavy reliance on prior knowledge. Here, we compare spatial filtering and CEBRA on human ECoG data to evaluate their effectiveness in extracting features that generalize across individuals, addressing a key challenge for adaptive and interpretable BCIs.

1. Experimental Recordings

The "Motor Basic" ECoG dataset (Miller et al., 2016) includes recordings of participants performing motor tasks in response to visual cues: rest (blank screen, ID 00), tongue movement ("TONGUE", ID 11), and finger movement ("FINGER", ID 12). Each session presented 30–75 cues with 2–3 second inter-trial intervals. Electrode locations are provided separately as $\mathbf{x} \times 3$ matrices representing spatial coordinates.

2. Methodology

Preprocessing

For both methods, trial data was created using stimulus IDs by identifying transitions and separating the corresponding start and end indices. This was combined with electrode locations and voltage signals into a unified raw object. Preprocessing was performed using MNE¹ and SciPy², including band-pass (Alpha: 8–13 Hz, Beta: 13–30 Hz, Gamma: 30–80 Hz) and band-stop filtering to isolate relevant components and remove noise. Feature vectors were constructed from the extracted frequency bands for both Spatial Filtering and CEBRA analyses. For Spatial Filtering, resting-state and movement data were paired to compute spatial filters and systematically explore feature extraction strategies.

Feature Extraction and Transformation

The spatial filtering method is based on Generalized Eigen Decomposition (GED), where the covariance matrices of the signal (S) and noise (R) are used to compute spatial filters according to Equation 1:

$$SW = RWA$$

where W is the matrix of spatial filters (eigenvectors), and Λ is the diagonal matrix of corresponding eigenvalues, each representing the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) for a given component. The spatial filters were applied to the raw signal to obtain components. The SNR is then calculated and components with top three SNR were presumed to capture the most informative neural activity.

CEBRA refined the neural data representation using contrastive learning. Neural activity associated with similar stimuli was mapped closer together in a latent space, while dissimilar

¹ <https://mne.tools/stable/index.html>

² <https://scipy.org/>

conditions were pushed further apart. The model transformed high-dimensional feature vectors into a compact, lower-dimensional space that preserved task-relevant structure while discarding irrelevant variability. Although CEBRA is primarily designed for spiking data, we adapted it to ECoG signals by extracting alpha, beta, and gamma band features, avoiding hyperparameter tuning to maintain adaptability. During transitions, initial attempts to introduce idle states degraded the performance by adding noise, so we preserved transitional information through careful preprocessing. Despite the analog nature of ECoG, CEBRA's convolutional and linear layers could still operate effectively on the processed inputs.

Classification

For both methods, extracted features were used for classification. The spatial filter approach utilized top filter features as input, while CEBRA-based classification used low-dimensional embeddings. LazyPredict³ was employed to compare multiple classification models and identify the most suitable one. The same classification model was applied to both approaches to ensure a fair comparison.

Results and Discussion

1. CEBRA

ECoG neural data was processed using the CEBRA pipeline (**Figure 1A**) with supervised learning applied separately for each subject and for a combined model across all subjects. The embeddings for individual subjects revealed that the two classes could be distinctly separated, albeit with some minor misclassifications (**Figure 1B**). We chose a 3D representation to remain consistent with CEBRA's original design and to better preserve the latent structure of the data.

³ <https://lazypredict.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Preliminary tests with 2D projections showed greater class overlap, suggesting that important discriminative information would be lost in lower dimensions. However, the spatial arrangement of the clusters varied between individuals, indicating a lack of alignment in embedding space across subjects (**Figure 1C**), where the 2D insets highlight the main two clusters along the y-z axis that represent the majority of data points. The few additional scattered points visible in the 3D plot correspond to a small number of samples, likely resulting from noise or proximity to other cortical regions, and do not substantially affect the overall class structure. To address this, we formed a cross-subject meta-population, pooling data across individuals who performed identical tasks under matched conditions. This approach improved latent space stability, leveraging the large-scale, stereotyped nature of ECoG signals to build a more generalizable and robust representation.

While the combined model successfully differentiated between the two classes, its performance on held-out subjects was poor, achieving no improvement over random chance in a binary classification task (**Figure 1F**). This suggests that although CEBRA effectively maps the neural data into a structured embedding space, it does not generalize well to unseen subjects without additional fine-tuning.

The diminished performance of CEBRA on human ECoG motor data, compared to its success with monkey and rat neural recordings (Miller et al., 2010), suggests that the increased complexity and abstract nature of human motor control introduce significant noise and complexity. This implies that decoding intended movement from human ECoG data becomes significantly more difficult with increased variability.

2. Spatial Filtering

Feature pairs were created as resting vs non-resting states, and Stimulus 11 vs Stimulus 12, focusing on the Alpha, Beta, and Gamma frequency bands. Amongst each Feature Pair, one was chosen to be contrasted against the other, highlighting the significant signal more prominently. Applying the GED method significantly improved the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), as shown below (**Figure 1E**). Solving the GED equation to identify data subspaces that maximize the difference between feature pairs resulted in significant increase in SNR. The filters were projected onto the raw data, yielding the most relevant spatial components. The signals were optimized by isolating the spatial components with the top three SNR values, guaranteeing that only the strongest features were preserved (**Figure 1D**). However, despite this enhancement, classification performance remained low when the extracted features were used as input for various machine learning models. Across multiple trials, these features alone did not provide sufficient discriminative power to achieve accurate stimulus classification (**Figure 1F**). This poor performance is likely due to the fact that GED maximizes SNR but does not explicitly optimize for class separability (Väisänen & Malmivuo, 2009). Task-relevant neural activity patterns are distributed across multiple components, rather than being concentrated in those with the highest SNR. By selecting only the top-ranked components, the method may exclude subtle and crucial features, resulting in an overall reduction in classification ability.

These findings suggest that while GED effectively improves data quality, additional feature extraction or modeling approaches may be necessary to achieve robust classification performance. Although CEBRA has demonstrated success in forming latent spaces for spiking and imaging data, its limited generalization in our setting highlights the need for more adaptable non-linear models. Future work could explore hybrid architectures that combine spatial filtering

with advanced deep learning techniques, such as pointwise convolutions or attention mechanisms, to better capture the complexity of human ECoG signals.

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MODEL	SPATIAL FILTER		CEBRA	
	FEATURE PAIR 1 (STIMULUS 11 - STIMULUS 12)	FEATURE PAIR 2 (REST STATE - NON REST STATE)	SUBJECT-HELD-OUT	TRIAL-HELD-OUT (20%)
LOBM	59%	51%	49%	67%
Random Forest	59%	64%	49%	67%
NuSVC	56%	45%	49%	67%
KNeighbors	53%	55%	49%	67%
svc	51%	54%	49%	67%
Quadratic Discriminant Analysis	50%	51%	47%	67%

Figure 1. Processing Pipelines and Performance Outcomes of Spatial Filter and CEBRA Methods.

A. Schematic representation of the data flow from ECoG electrodes to model training. Neural signals are recorded, relevant stimulus-active intervals are extracted, and the processed data is fed into a CEBRA deep neural network trained with a contrastive loss function.

B. Low-dimensional embeddings of individual subjects' neural data after transformation by the CEBRA model, illustrating the learned structure of neural representations.

C. A generalized CEBRA model trained on data from all subjects embeds each subject's neural data into a shared low-dimensional space. The resulting embeddings serve as input for a trained classifier to predict stimulus class. Insets highlight the two main clusters along the y-z axis, showing distinct separation between stimulus classes.

D. GED equation visualization, where the covariance matrix of the signal (S) and the covariance matrix of noise (R) are used to compute the spatial filters enhancing SNR by optimizing the spatial representation of the signal.

E. Illustration of how GED improves SNR across a selected frequency band. *Upper Graph:* Power spectral densities for three channels of the raw signal, with the gray bar indicating the frequency band used to estimate the spatial filters. Channels were selected based on the highest SNR in the frequency range. *Lower Graph:* Power spectral densities for the first three components after applying filter, showing an improved SNR and distinct peaks.

F. Classification performance of various models trained on neural data transformed by spatial filtering** and the CEBRA deep neural network.

**Classification of Spatial Filtered data was done by Trial Held-Out (20%)

3. Conclusions

Both Spatial Filtering and CEBRA exhibited limited classification performance using machine learning approaches, indicating that these methods alone do not provide sufficient discriminatory power for stimulus classification. However, each method addresses different challenges. GED cleaned the data while enhancing the SNR with minimal computational cost, which is suitable for real-time applications. In contrast, CEBRA preserved task-relevant structures, capturing neural variability. However, further work is needed to explore domain adaptation or subject-specific fine-tuning to improve generalization.

The integration of these approaches has the potential to improve the adaptability and robustness of BCIs only when combined with other pre-processing and feature extraction techniques. This highlights the critical need for the development of hybrid methods, driving progress toward more effective and universally applicable BCIs.

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